

Project Management and Coordination/ D4.1

WP4, T4.1 Project coordination: contractual, financial and quality management

Authors: Stefania De Santi (APRE)

Technical references

Project Acronym	EIC COMMUNITIES
Project Title	Building Synergies and Communities around EIC Portfolios to raise the impact of the EIC deep tech research
Project Coordinator	Stefania De Santi APRE desanti@apre.it
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Lead beneficiary	1 - APRE
Contributing beneficiary/ies	ICONS, EurA, EBN
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* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1.0	16.10.23	APRE	Stefania De Santi

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1. Executive summary

The current document, titled Quality Management Plan (QMP), has been developed within the framework of EIC Communities which is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No . 101105050.

The **main objectives** of the QMP are to:

- ensure smooth implementation and timely accomplishment of EIC Communities activities
- guarantee the quality of the activities and deliverables of the project in line with the contractual obligations enclosed in the Grant Agreement and in compliance with the Consortium Agreement signed by all EIC Communities beneficiaries.

To this end, the QMP provides an overview of the management structure, describes the responsibilities of the partners, defines the procedures for ensuring the quality of project deliverables and for dissemination within and outside the consortium as well as delineates procedures for progress monitoring and reporting.

Important remarks:

- compliance with the QMP is mandatory for all project partners;
- the QMP complements and does not replace the Grant Agreement signed with the EC, its Annexes, and the Consortium Agreement of the project.

2. EIC Communities Management Structure

The EIC Communities management structure is composed of two main management bodies:

- **The Coordinator (APRE)** – is responsible for the financial, administrative and operative management and coordination of the consortium and project activities. The Project Coordinator (PCoo) is responsible for the overall technical, the administrative and financial co-ordination of the project, the control of the project scheduling and achievements, the generation of corrective actions, the submission to the Commission of the deliverables and regular reports of progress and resource expenditure, the verification of the milestones achieved, the internal smooth communication among all partners, the organization and chairing of the General Assembly.
- **General Assembly (GA)**- is the decision-making body of the consortium. The GA is composed of one representative of each partner institution and is chaired by the Project Coordinator. Each partner is responsible to carry out the activities described in the work plan and to answer to the Project Coordinator requests on time. The Project Coordinator organizes the meetings with the GA, chairs the meetings, prepares the agenda and the minutes. Each partner's representative has one vote. The decisions are taken by consensus or by majority of the votes cast.

3. EIC Communities deliverables

According to the DoA, every deliverable is under the responsibility of a specific Lead Beneficiary (LB) and is the outcome of a specific task, linked to a work package. The Lead Beneficiary responsible for the deliverable guarantees the quality, completeness, and timely submission of the document.

All deliverables must follow the established EIC Communities deliverable template, which has been shared with all partners and is available to all partners in the dedicated area of Share point.

3.1. File naming

With reference to electronic files, the following guidelines will be followed:

- File name should preferably not exceed 30 characters. The deliverable number and official name as stated in the Grant Agreement should be part of the file name.
- The author of the file puts the name of his/her organisation in the file name.
- The file name contains the date of the last modification.

[Ex. D4.1 Quality Management Plan APRE_31oct23](#)

- In the case of a deliverable revision by another partner, the revising partner adds, as the end of the file name, an abbreviation '_rev_' and the name of his/her organisation.

[Ex. D4.1 Quality Management Plan APRE_31oct23_rev_Ben](#)

3.2. Quality assurance procedure

The standard quality assurance process is the following:

Step 1): At least 20 working days before the submission deadline, a draft deliverable is shared by the Lead Beneficiary with Task Supporters and the relevant WP leader for revision. Preferably, the draft deliverable should be shared in the form of an online document in order to enable access of multiple persons simultaneously. In this case, the above rules concerning file naming for revision purposes do not apply.

Step 2): Task Supporters, the WP leader, and, if relevant, other internal reviewers, have a maximum of 8 working days to provide their comments and feedback. The comments/feedback shall be always provided in the track-changes mode.

Step 3): The Lead Beneficiary has a maximum of 7 working days to address the comments, including, if necessary, further consultations with the Task Supporters and the WP leader.

Step 4): At least 4/5 days before the submission deadline, the revised deliverable is sent by the Lead Beneficiary to the Coordinator for final revision. In the case the coordinator has comments/feedback, the Lead Beneficiary will address them as soon as possible, without undue delay, to ensure timely submission.

Step 5): The Coordinator submits the final deliverable in the *Funding&Tenders Portal*. The Coordinator is the only one responsible for submitting deliverables in the Portal.

The table below presents all project deliverables, the respective deliverable leaders and dates relevant for the quality assurance process and for the deliverable submission. It should be noted that these are the suggested latest dates. However, Lead Beneficiaries are encouraged to speed up the quality assurance process and submit first versions of their respective deliverables before the indicated dates, if possible.

Table 1

Del.	Deliverable name	Deliverable Leader	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Submission date
D1.1	Needs assessment and the refinement of portfolios selection	EurA	10/11/2023	18/11/2023	25/11/2023	29/11/2023	M3 30/11/2023
D1.2	Strategy for EIC PMs and EIC meaningful engagement in EIC communities	EurA	10/06/2024	18/06/2024	25/06/2024	29/06/2024	M10 30/06/2024
D1.3	Strategy for EIC PMs and EIC meaningful engagement in EIC communities - Update	EurA	05/12/2025	13/12/2025	20/12/2025	28/12/2025	M28 31/12/2025 (*timing has been anticipated due to Christmas holidays)
D1.4	Online portfolio ecosystem database	EIC ICONS	08/12/2023	16/12/2023	23/12/2023	28/12/2023	M4 31/12/2023
D1.5	Online portfolio ecosystem database – 2nd version	EIC ICONS	09/06/2024	17/06/2024	24/06/2024	29/06/2024	M10 30/06/2024
D1.6	Online portfolio ecosystem	EIC ICONS	07/02/2026	15/02/2026	22/02/2026	27/02/2026	M30 28/02/2026

	database – 3rd version						
D1.7	Knowledge base on how to build and promote sustainable and inclusive communities around EIC portfolios	EurA	11/01/2024	19/01/2024	26/01/2024	30/01/2024	M5 31/01/2024
D1.8	New visions and policy recommendations for future deep-tech research and innovation	EurA	08/12/2025	16/12/2025	23/12/2025	28/12/2025	M28 31/12/2025
D2.1	CoPs: Governance structure and management	EBN	08/12/2023	16/12/2023	23/12/2023	28/12/2023	M4 31/12/2023
D2.2	CoP animation – 1st version	EBN	10/06/2024	18/06/2024	25/06/2024	29/06/2024	M10 30/06/2024
D2.3	CoP animation – 2nd version	EBN	08/02/2026	16/02/2026	23/02/2026	27/02/2026	M30 28/02/2026
D2.4	Stakeholder engagement strategy in the green, digital/industry/space and health CoPs	EURA	13/02/2024	17/02/2024	22/02/2024	27/02/2024	M6 28/02/2024
D2.5	Report on the outcomes of activities carried out in the green, digital/industry/space and health thematic hub – first version	APRE	10/11/2024	18/11/2024	25/11/2024	29/11/2024	M15 30/11/2024

D2.6	Report on the outcomes of activities carried out in the green, digital/industry/space and health thematic hub - second version	APRE	08/02/2026	16/02/2026	23/02/2026	27/02/2026	M30 28/02/2026
D2.7	Report on the outcomes of CoP activities - first version	EBN	10/11/2024	18/11/2024	25/11/2024	29/11/2024	M15 30/11/2024
D2.8	Report on the outcomes of CoP activities - second version	EBN	08/02/2026	16/02/2026	23/02/2026	27/02/2026	M30 28/02/2026
D2.9	Best Practices collection	EBN	08/02/2026	16/02/2026	23/02/2026	27/02/2026	M30 28/02/2026
D2.10	Future Tech Week first report	ICONS	08/02/2025	16/02/2025	23/02/2025	27/02/2025	M18 28/02/2025
D2.11	Future Tech Week second report	ICONS	08/02/2026	16/02/2026	23/02/2026	27/02/2026	M30 28/02/2026
D3.1	Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities	ICONS	08/02/2024	16/02/2024	23/02/2024	27/02/2024	M6 28/02/2024
D3.2	Updated Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities	ICONS	08/02/2025	16/02/2025	23/02/2025	27/02/2025	M18 28/02/2025

D3.3	Sustainability Strategy (including Dissemination, exploitation and communication)	ICONS	08/02/2026	16/02/2026	23/02/2026	27/02/2026	M30 28/02/2026
D3.4	First report on communication and dissemination activities and impact analysis	ICONS	10/11/2024	18/11/2024	25/11/2024	29/11/2024	M15 30/11/2024
D3.5	Second report on communication and dissemination activities and impact analysis	ICONS	08/02/2026	16/02/2026	23/02/2026	27/02/2026	M30 28/02/2026
D3.6	Website and project logo	ICONS	11/10/2023	19/10/2023	26/10/2023	30/10/2023	M2 31/10/2023
D 4.1	Management and Quality Plan	APRE	11/10/2023	19/10/2023	26/10/2023	30/10/2023	M2 31/10/2023
D 4.2	Data Management Plan and Ethics – first review	APRE	11/08/2024	19/08/2024	26/08/2024	30/08/2024	M12 31/08/2024
D 4.3	Data Management Plan and Ethics – second review	APRE	08/02/2026	16/02/2026	23/02/2026	27/02/2026	M30 28/02/2026
D 4.4	Data Management Plan and Ethics	APRE	08/02/2024	16/02/2024	23/02/2024	27/02/2024	M6 28/02/2024
D4.5	Reporting Period 1 Technical/scientific review meeting documents	APRE	11/07/2024	19/07/2024	26/07/2024	30/07/2024	M11 31/07/2024
D4.6	Reporting Period 2	APRE	11/01/2026	19/01/2026	26/01/2026	30/01/2026	31/01/2026

	Technical/scientific review meeting documents						
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4. Communication

4.1.1. Internal communication within the Consortium

The Coordinator has the main responsibility of ensuring smooth and effective internal communication. Communication between Beneficiaries will primarily take place through online communication tools, namely emails and online calls and meetings. A contact list, featuring the relevant contact details for each Beneficiary has been created at M1 and is available in the Teams Project Group: (dedicated file “**Contact list.xlsx**”). It will be regularly updated to ensure that possible staff rotations are timely addressed and do not affect the project implementation. To that end, in the event of any change in the contact details or in the project team, partners should notify the Coordinator, who will update the mailing list accordingly and without any delay.

From the mailing list, a project email has been created:

- all@eicommunities.eu used for: General Events notice, Reporting activities, Amendments information, Annual meeting invitation, Notice social media updates. In the event of any change in the contact details or in the project team, partners should notify ICONS, who will update the mailing list accordingly and without any delay.

Whatever email is used, Beneficiaries always:

- use a narrative subject beginning with ‘EIC Communities’
- inform and update the partners on time about the work you performed
- explain what is expected: is it feedback (from whom and by when), or is it just information,
- avoid attachments (if possible), save them in the concerned shared space (e.g., WP folder),
- Inform the Coordinator if you want to add (or to remove) someone from your organization contacts, mentioning the role, the email and in which mailing list to be added.

As general rule, it seeks to circulate emails from EIC Communities to all members no more than once per day, for not lose track of what’s important and might overlook the emails that ask for timely contribution.

In relation to internal meetings, according to the Consortium Agreement and the DoA, EIC Communities GA will convey once a month virtually for ordinary meetings and in M1, in M14 and in M29 on-site, as shown by the table below, and at any time upon request of 2 Members of the GA.

APRE is responsible for meetings’ organisation, logistics and minute drafting.

Table 2

Project month	Meeting location/host	Purpose
M1	Rome/APRE	Kick of Meeting
M14	To be decided	GA meeting
M29	To be decided	GA meeting

Communication concerning important issues and strategic decision-making (e.g. sending deliverables, planning meetings, reporting risks or deviations from the DOA, etc.), as well as any formal communication (e.g. project meetings), should be documented in writing (e.g. by preparing the meeting minutes, maintaining an electronic (e.g. emails) or paper copy records). Informal communication taking place between Beneficiaries and concerning less significant issues of every-day project implementation (through MS Teams, informal emails, etc.) may not be documented.

The Coordinator and the WP Leaders are expected to communicate regularly with the project partners so as to follow closely the project and work packages progress, and identify in time potential deviations. Close collaboration and communication between project partners is essential and will be encouraged by the Coordinator especially in cases where they have to cooperate in order to perform specific tasks.

4.1.2. External communication

4.1.2.1. Communication with the EC

The Coordinator (APRE) is the sole responsible for the communication with the Project Officer (PO) with respect to the project. Project partners should not contact the PO without previous discussion with APRE. Only in exceptional cases, and if the PO requires so, may a project partner directly contact the PO. In such a case the Coordinator shall be kept fully informed (in writing) about the content of the communication.

The Coordinator has the responsibility of submitting to the EC all reports and deliverables of the project. They also provide the EC with any additional information and/or clarification that have been requested by the EC services. Finally, the Coordinator will keep all Beneficiaries informed about any important communication with the EC.

4.1.2.2. Communication with third parties

Project partners may and should communicate with third parties (e.g., national authorities, local stakeholders, other EU-funded projects) within the context of the project. In all external communications, a reference to the project should be made (e.g., project acronym, EU programme, GA No).

Communication and actions towards third parties will be reported to the GA and will be mentioned in the project technical reporting to give evidence of the developed relations and interactions.

4.1.3. Complaints and conflict resolution

Each WP leader will immediately notify the Coordinator about any event or circumstance that may significantly affect the performance of the work executed in the frame of their work package (e.g. suggestions for considerable improvements and modifications/changes in the methodology, timetable, and task allocation, potential delays, disputes between partners, etc.).

The Coordinator will be responsible for and will take the necessary steps to resolve the abovementioned issues by consulting with the relevant WP leaders and any partner directly involved in the respective Work Package. In the case of a dispute, the following Conflict Resolution Procedure will apply: i) the disputing parties will inform the respective WP leader, ii) if the WP leader is not able to resolve the problem, they will inform the Coordinator, iii) The Coordinator will discuss the issue with the GA and, after reaching an internal agreement, will get in contact with the disputing parties aiming at implementing the agreed decision, iv) if the issue is still not solved, the matter will be taken for a virtual vote at an extraordinary GA virtual meeting.

Further details with respect to decision-making, conflict resolution as well as the management of internal administrative and financial issues are incorporated in the project's Consortium Agreement. When necessary, the Coordinator will inform the EC requesting feedback.

5. Progress reporting

5.1.1. Internal reporting

In addition to EC formal reporting obligations, the consortium will carry out 3 internal reports (at M10, M20 and M30) that will consist of a brief activity report and a financial report of each Beneficiary. Internal reporting will aim at monitoring the work performed by each partner and at guaranteeing a coordinated management of both project activities and resources, with the view to timely detection of risks to project implementation and effective resolution of identified problems.

For the purpose of collecting all necessary information in a coordinated manner, the Coordinator will prepare a dedicated reporting tool that each partner will be requested to fill in at M10, M20, and M30.

The reporting tool will consist of:

- The financial report sheet where each partner will provide the relevant financial information concerning their performance in the project (regarding the use of personnel costs as well as other direct costs and related indirect costs) for the following periods: M1-M9, M10-M19, M20-M29.
- The activities report sheet where each partner will provide information about the activities performed in tasks they are involved in and the justifications related to the expenditure of budget for travel and other goods and services, also linked to the different tasks for the following periods: M1-M9, M10-M19, M20-M29.
- Two last sheets (financial statement and financial monitoring) will be filled automatically and will be locked for any changes, as they enclose formulas that directly calculate all the sums, indirect costs, left budget, etc., according to the EC financial rules.

The internal reporting will be organized and led by the Coordinator, who will provide the consortium with all necessary guidance and advice on the reporting process and tools. The reporting tool will be used both for the interim informal reports (M10, M20, M30) and in preparation of the contractual periodic reports (M15, M30), so that also the information due officially to the EC will be prepared, assessed, and monitored in a homogeneous way.

The tool will be shared with each Beneficiary 30 days before the end of the concerned period. The financial data must reflect the activities described by each partner, meaning that, for example, if there are no activities reported in a specific task, there cannot be financial efforts declared in that task.

Each reporting tool provided by each Beneficiary will need to be reviewed and approved by the Coordinator. All collected reporting tools will be stored by the Coordinator in a separate dedicated and secure file on the Coordinator's server.

In case the financial and/or technical progress will be affected by delays or problems in the implementation, the coordinator may request additional internal monitoring to better check the project state of art and adopt in agreement with the GA corrective measures.

5.1.2. Reporting to the EC

The Coordinator is responsible for the periodic reports that will be prepared with the contribution of all Beneficiaries and then officially submitted through the *Funding and Tenders Portal*. Within EIC Communities, two official reports are foreseen, namely at M15 and M30. The abovementioned reports will enclose information about how the project is progressing both from a technical and a financial point of view. All partners have part of the responsibility to deliver the reports, meaning that they have to send their inputs for the report to the Coordinator in due time when requested and, with reference to the technical report, each Work Package Leader is directly responsible for the elaboration of the chapters related to their respective WPs, also gathering contributions from the task leaders. All the steps and the relative deadlines will be summarized within precise and detailed communications from the Coordinator preceding each reporting period. The reports will be submitted by the Coordinator online on the official EC templates and they will include:

- an overview of the activities carried out in the concerned period,
- a description of the progress achieved towards the objectives and the milestones planned,
- the deliverables produced,
- the identification of possible problems faced and the corrective actions taken or planned,
- information and justification about the resources used/deployed by each beneficiary.

Furthermore, according to the official Horizon Europe legal and financial rules.

The consortium will submit the periodic report and the final report within 60 days following the end of the reporting period.

6. Appendix A - EIC Communities Gantt Chart

Figure 1

Work Packages/Tasks	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	
	set-23	ott-23	nov-23	dic-23	gen-24	feb-24	mar-24	apr-24	mag-24	giu-24	lug-24	ago-24	set-24	ott-24	nov-24	dic-24	gen-25	feb-25	mar-25	apr-25	mag-25	giu-25	lug-25	ago-25	set-25	ott-25	nov-25	dic-25	gen-26	feb-26	
WP1 A systematic approach to expanding EIC portfolios into EIC deep-tech communities																															
T11 need assessment, fining-up of EIC portfolio selection and strategy to engage EIC PMs in EIC communities (EurA + APPE, EBN)		Co-creation Brussels	Needs assessment and the refinement of workshop practices selection (D11)							Strategy for EIC PMs and EIC meaningful engagement in EIC communities (D12)																Assessment meeting in Brussels in connection with workshop T11					
T12 EIC portfolio ecosystem analysis and database (ICONS + All)				On-line EIC portfolio ecosystem database (D14)				Database represented in project website		Update On-line EIC portfolio ecosystem database (D15)																					Update On-line EIC portfolio ecosystem database (D16)
T13 diverse and gender inclusive communities around EIC portfolios (EurA + APPE)		Identification of good practices and formats to foster and promote inclusive communities			set of good practices, guidelines and lesson learnt (D17)																										
T14 Co-creation of new visions, direction and policy recommendations for FSU in future deep-tech (EurA + All)											Knowledge creation phase					Sense making phase for co-design of strategic roadmaps for EIC challenge (on-line)			making and acting phase								co-design of strategic roadmaps for EIC challenge (Brussels)	in of Strategic Roadmap in an on-line policy workshop with EU policy makers and decision makers	new visions and policy recommendations for future deep-tech research and innovation (D18)		

Figure 2

Work Packages/Tasks	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	
	set-23	ott-23	nov-23	dic-23	gen-24	feb-24	mar-24	apr-24	mag-24	giu-24	lug-24	ago-24	set-24	ott-24	nov-24	dic-24	gen-25	feb-25	mar-25	apr-25	mag-25	giu-25	lug-25	ago-25	set-25	ott-25	nov-25	dic-25	gen-26	feb-26	
WP2 Community and synergy building between EIC portfolios and projects																															
T2.1 Establishment of the management of CoPs (EurA + All)	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoPs: Governance structure and management (D.2.1) CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoPs: Governance structure and management (D.2.1) CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoP managers monthly report to coordinator	CoPs: Governance structure and management (D.2.1) CoP managers monthly report to coordinator								
T2.3 Building synergies between projects in the three portfolio hubs (APPE + EBN and EurA)				On-line co-creation workshop in each CoP						On-line pitching sessions in each portfolio hub - on-line webinars				the outcomes of activities carried out in the thematic hubs (D.2.5)												On-line pitching sessions in each portfolio hub - on-line webinars					On-line pitching sessions in each portfolio hub - on-line webinars
T2.4 Community building within the CoPs (EBN + All)				Stakeholder engagement strategy (D.2.4)						On-line Portfolio Days in each CoP (date TBD) - thematic workshops				Report on the outcomes of the CoP activities (D.2.5)												On-line Portfolio Days in each CoP (date TBD) - thematic workshops					Report on the outcomes of the CoP activities (D.2.6)
T2.5 Interaction across the CoP and beyond (EBN + All)									on-line Information Day (date TBD)					Report on the outcomes of CoP activities - first version (D.2.7)					Future Tech Week report (D.2.8)							By MS2 bilateral exchanges between projects	the results of bilateral exchanges translated in case studies				Report on the outcomes of the CoP activities - second version (D.2.8)

Figure 3

Work Packages/Tasks	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	
	set-23	ott-23	nov-23	dic-23	gen-24	feb-24	mar-24	apr-24	mag-24	giu-24	lug-24	ago-24	set-24	ott-24	nov-24	dic-24	gen-25	feb-25	mar-25	apr-25	mag-25	giu-25	lug-25	ago-25	set-25	ott-25	nov-25	dic-25	gen-26	feb-26	
WP3 - Raising visibility and impacts																															
T3.1 Strategy design and implementation (ICONS + All)		logo and web page (D.3)			Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results (D.3.1)														Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results (D.3.2)												
T3.4 Impact assessment and sustainability (ICONS + All)															Report on communication and dissemination on activities and impact analysis (D.3.4)																Sustainability strategy (D.3.3)
WP4 - Project management and coordination																															
T4.1 Project coordination: contractual, financial and quality management (APPE + All)		Management and Quality plan (D.4.1)								Interim report by partners (activity and financial) (D.4.4)					Submission interim report to EC						Interim report by partner (activity and financial)										Reporting period 2: technical review meeting (D.4.4)
T4.2 Project meetings (APPE + All)	kick off meeting													Consortium meeting for the preparation of the interim report																	Consortium meeting for the preparation of the final report
T4.3 Data management and ethics (APPE + All)					Management of Plan and Ethics (D.4.4)									Management of Plan and Ethics (D.4.4)																	Management of Plan and Ethics (D.4.4)

7. Appendix B - EIC Communities Work Packages structure

Figure 4

8. Appendix C - EIC Communities Resources to be committed

Table 3

Staff effort per participant					
<i>Grant Preparation (Work packages - Effort screen) — Enter the info.</i>					
Participant	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	Total Person-Months
1 - APRE	5.00	15.00	8.00	17.00	45.00
2 - ICONS	4.50	3.50	24.00	1.50	33.50
3 - EBN	1.00	17.00	2.50	1.50	22.00
4 - EurA	18.00	11.00	4.00	1.50	34.50
Total Person-Months	28.50	46.50	38.50	21.50	135.00

